

Title: Bitcoin, Ethereum - Beyond FinTech towards a Decentralized Future

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INTRODUCTION:

Abstract: Over the last few years we have seen lot of new avenues where Cryptocurrency and Blockchain have been explored. But at the fundamental level we search for use cases and mostly keep ourselves focused on implementing solutions for these problems. Either we take Bitcoin & Ethereum as a payment medium for complex use cases or use the smart contract technology to implement some form of exchange platform with tokenomics to support an execution in a definitive application or business scenario. Unfortunately the core power of Bitcoin & Ethereum is not realized which was envisioned where they wanted Cryptocurrency to not only be the internet of money and world computer but also the window to a Decentralized future where we trust the trust less peer to peer network. Today most of the people who use Bitcoin is either as Digital Gold or they think it as a speculative investment which is the case with other cryptocurrency as well. Ethereum's still best use case has been ICOs while it is reaching its maximum capacity, still the effort for next horizon in smart contracts have been mostly into FinTech space creating Decentralized exchanges or smart escrows. While imagining Decentralized future we have to imagine beyond the confines of just the Blockchain and the current user base. We need to get beyond the current trappings of current use cases and dream bigger disruptive innovations that a Decentralized future can bring. A Decentralized future is more revolutionary than Agile, Lean enterprise movement, we are today looking at disrupting societies, we are looking at challenging orthodox and archaic dogmas like Communism and to some extent even Democracy. Thanks to technological growth and thanks to Cryptocurrency and Blockchain we are standing at a moment in history where we talk about thinking things from a different outlook where like a network anyone can join anyone an fall back and still the ideology and the growth of a network will still go on and still the governance can happen on chain. And with smart contracts and automation we no more need to take all decisions based on human trust. Again many may see a flip side but we are already living in a technological advanced automated future. Blockchain, Cryptocurrency can only help democratize and leverage these technologies for us to focus beyond the trappings of earthly issue and focus on things that matter and bring to a Decentralized future.